

A grammar-licensed treebank of Czech*

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Abstract

We describe main features of a treebank of Czech, licensed by an HPSG-style grammar. The grammar interacts with corpus texts, preprocessed by morphological analysis and morphological disambiguation, a (largely) stochastic dependency parser and subsequent transformation into phrase-structure trees. The resulting trees, including functional and categorial information on words and phrases, are represented as typed feature structures. The grammar cooperates with a valency lexicon: the actual data are matched with surface valency frames, derived by lexical rules from predicate-argument structures in the lexicon. If the match is successful, the resulting annotation is enriched with information derived from the parsed data and from the lexicon. The paper concludes with an evaluation of the individual processing steps.

1 Introduction

There may be different opinions about the status of *langue* and *parole*, reflected both in linguistics and in NLP by the preference of rationalist or empirical methods, but the continuing coexistence of (hand-crafted) grammars as an approximation of language as a system and (real-text) corpora as an expression of language use indicates that the two notions are (indeed) two sides of a coin. We believe that a corpus, annotated by theoretically motivated and explicitly defined categories and structures, may in fact be that coin. The empirical and the theoretical sides of linguistics meet in the annotation of a corpus.

There is not a single proper way for such an annotation. Many potential users may prefer categories common in traditional grammar books but not much used in NLP, corpus linguistics or most linguistic theories, such as those treating analytical

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verbal forms as a part of morphology. We propose a solution that reconciles the paradigmatic and syntagmatic view of complex forms.

The definition of the annotation scheme and content is a de facto competence grammar. In addition to its theoretical appeal, the formal definition may support checking of both the data and the grammar, help to formulate efficient queries, offer concordances as correctly displayed structures, provide conversions to different representations, and assist grammar development.

In this paper, we focus on the way the grammar interacts with the corpus texts, pre-processed by a (largely) stochastic tool. First, the general approach is outlined and the objectives of developing a grammar-licensed treebank are specified in §2. Then the steps of processing an input text, including stochastic parsing, are briefly described in §3. Next, §4 focuses on the annotation format: a constituency-based tree structure, including categorial information in words and phrases. The core of the paper is a description of the grammar and the lexicon (§5). As an important step, grammar rules (“principles”) make sure that the valency information is matched with actual data (i.e., that valency requirements are satisfied). Finally, §6 is devoted to an evaluation of several processing stages, before some issues and perspectives are discussed in §7.

2 An overview of the approach

In addition to an annotation scheme, we want the treebank to be consistent with theoretically motivated linguistic patterns. The collection of constraints on the annotation format and its content are viewed as a formal grammar. The grammar necessarily undergenerates due to *langue/parole* differences, insufficient coverage of *langue*, or simply because of errors in the data or in a previous processing step. Rather than excluding sentences failing the grammaticality test from the treebank, such sentences are flagged and reasons for the failure are examined.

However, there is no guarantee that sentences passing the test are 100% correct either. The grammar overgenerates – the space of possible language expressions is restricted by specifying phenomena-specific constraints, leaving difficult phenomena unchecked. In fact, the grammar, due to its modularity, can be set to a more or less restrictive mode. This scenario also allows for modular and incremental grammar development.¹

The grammar augments the annotation produced by the stochastic parser and checks its consistency. It does so (i) by matching lexical information (esp. valency), obtained from external lexica, with the parsed texts and (ii) by projecting lexical information into phrasal nodes.

By matching treebank data with constraints of the grammar we can detect errors in the treebank data, the grammar and the lexical specifications, explore un-

¹In the terminology of [7] the grammar operates in a satisfiability-based rather than validity-based setup: a string is licensed if all constraints in the grammar are satisfied. The more constraints, the fewer strings are licensed; an empty grammar licenses any string.

derstudied linguistic phenomena, and thus provide necessary feedback leading to improvements in the grammar, the lexicon and the treebank annotation.

In order to handle large data (in the order of hundreds of millions of word tokens), the treebank annotation is generated by software tools only, without any manual intervention, including (stochastic) parsing and (grammar-based) checking.

To satisfy users (and applications) of different tastes, the resulting annotation is available in different formats (e.g. a constituency-based or dependency-based one), both for viewing and export.

Many treebanks are built only by human effort and/or by applying stochastic parsers, but we are not unique in the use of hand-crafted rule-based methods either. There are a number of projects relying on hand-crafted lexica, such as *PDT-VALLEX* [2], *CCGbank* [5], *FrameNet* [12], *PropBank* [1], *TüBa-D/Z Valency Lexicon* [3], or grammars, such as *LinGO Redwoods* [11], *Alpino* [21], *Norgram* [16], *BulTreeBank* [17], or *Sktadnica* [23]. Our approach is different in that it combines stochastic parse of unrestricted texts with hand-crafted grammar and lexicon.

3 Processing the input text

The input text is morphologically analyzed and tagged by a combination of a rule-based disambiguation module and a stochastic tagger. It is then parsed by Malt-Parser, a stochastic dependency parser [10]. In order to improve the accuracy of the parser, the text is partially lexically simplified: several groups of syntactically equivalent words, e.g. personal proper nouns or numerals, are replaced by equivalent proxies, reducing lexical and formal variability of the text by ca. 20%. The parser is trained on a text simplified in this way [6]. The result, with the original forms restored, is a skeletal parse with functional annotation. Dependency trees are then converted to phrase-structure trees, where each terminal node is assigned a morphosyntactic description and a syntactic function. Finally, the morphological and syntactic annotation are transformed into a typed feature structure in the HPSG style.

For a sample sentence (1) we show its dependency structure in the PDT format [13], produced by the stochastic parser (Fig. 1), and its phrase structure (Fig. 2) after the conversion.

- (1) Přemýšlel jsem o dobru a zlu.
Thought AUX-1SG about good and evil.
'I was thinking about good and evil.'

In Fig. 1, every node except for the top node is assigned a word form and a syntactic function: Pred is assigned to the verbal predicate of the sentence, conjunction *a* represents Coord(ination) of objects as conjuncts (Obj_Co), while AuxV, AuxP and AuxK denote auxiliary verb, preposition and full stop, respectively.

The phrase structure in Fig. 2 shows terminal and nonterminal nodes with their syntactic functions. Three kinds of heads are distinguished: Head, DeepHead and

Figure 1: Input dependency structure of sentence (1)

SurfHead, where SurfHead is assigned to the auxiliary verb *jsem* and the preposition *o*, DeepHead to the VP headed by the content verb *přemýšlel* and to the coordinated structure consisting of two conjuncts (assigned the CoMemb function) and a coordinating conjunction *a* (CoConj). The prepositional phrase *o dobru a zlu* ‘about good and evil’ is Obj(ect) of the verb *přemýšlel*. (Syntactic annotation is discussed in §4.)

In the current setup, the parser produces a single fully disambiguated result for each sentence,² although the resulting functional labels may fold some cases of structural ambiguities, such as PP-attachment. In the next step (augmentation and

²We plan to test an n-best or voting scenario, involving several parsers.

Figure 2: Output phrase-structure tree for sentence (1)

checking by the grammar), any such ambiguities are either resolved, or preserved,³ while some additional ambiguities may occur when more information is added (e.g. with a more detailed classification of adverbials). Most of these ambiguities are represented as underspecification rather than disjunction.

4 The annotation format

Linguistic categories and structures in the data are modeled as typed feature structures using: (i) format declaration for lexical and phrasal categories as a type hierarchy with multiple inheritance; and (ii) constraints on complex relationships between the values, representing various phenomena (agreement, government, grammatical control).

Each word form is assigned appropriate cross-classifying properties of three kinds: morphological (inflectional), syntactic and semantic (lexical) (cf. [15]). Traditional parts of speech are, in fact, a mix of these three criteria. For some word classes the three criteria coincide: nouns refer to entities (semantic criterion), decline according to nominal paradigms (morphological criterion) and occur in nominal positions (syntactic criterion). In Czech, their morphological categories reflect syntactic function by case and an approximation of cardinality by grammatical number, while they show the inherent (lexical) property of grammatical gender. On the other hand, numerals and pronouns are defined by purely semantic criteria, but in other aspects cardinal numerals and personal pronouns behave like nouns, whereas ordinal numerals and possessive pronouns behave like adjectives, including the appropriate morphological categories.

In our cross-classification we also model some regular derivational relations: deverbal nouns and adjectives (inflectional classes) are derived from verbs (lexical class), while possessive adjectives are derived from nouns. An example of morphological annotation is presented in Fig. 3 below.

<i>iNoun_lVerb_sNoun</i>	
iLemma	<i>neprověření</i>
iNum	<i>pl</i>
iGend	<i>n</i>
iCase	<i>inst</i>
lLemma	<i>prověřit</i>
lPol	<i>minus</i>
lAspect	<i>perf</i>

Figure 3: Morphological annotation of the word form *neprověřeními* ‘(with) non-verifications’ as a typed feature structure

³The latter option is not implemented yet.

In Fig. 3 the three-dimensional typed feature structure for the word form *neprověřenými* ‘(with) non-verifications’ is shown: the form is a negative plural instrumental form of a neuter deverbal noun: *neprověřenými* (thus inflectional Number (iNum) is *plural*, inflectional Gender (iGend) is specified as *neuter*, which is true for all deverbal nouns, and inflectional Case (iCase) is equal to *instrumental*). It declines as a noun (“inflectional noun” is iNoun), it is derived by a regular derivation from the lexical Verb *prověřit* ‘verify’ (lVerb) and it has a nominal syntactic distribution (sNoun). In a typed feature structure used for the description of linguistic objects, this triple of values is rendered as a complex type *iNoun_lVerb_sNoun*. The derivation is also reflected in two kinds of lemmas: inflectional lemma (iLemma) *neprověření* and lexical/semantic lemma (lLemma) *prověřit*). The lexical properties of polarity (lPol) and aspect (lAspect) specify the base verb as negated and perfective.

An additional dimension is used to identify morphological categories of analytical verb forms since we want to accommodate interpretations of expressions consisting of one or more function (auxiliary) words and a content word, mainly those traditionally viewed as belonging to the domain of analytical morphology. This “analytical” word class dimension specifies categories such as tense, mood, and voice.

The phrase-structure trees use a combination of binary and flat branching. The constituents are assigned syntactic functions, such as subject, attribute, object, etc. (cf. Fig. 2). In headed structures,⁴ the number and properties of non-head daughters are determined by the valency of the head daughter (assigned the Head syntactic function). Optional modifiers are added non-deterministically to the list of complements.⁵ Heads can be further distinguished as surface and deep. This distinction is used in phrases including function words: e.g., in prepositional phrases, where the preposition is the surface head (SurfHead) and the noun phrase is the deep head (DeepHead). An unqualified head is both a surface and a deep head. This type of classification of heads allows for interpreting syntactic structures according to users’ preferences as constituency or dependency trees, and as surface or deep structures.

5 The grammar

The grammar treats the result of the stochastic parser as a set of constraints, assumed to be true about a sentence. The data format and the constraints are checked for consistency, and additional constraints originating in the grammar and external lexica are matched with those present in the data. As a result, lexical information is projected from the leaves of the syntactic tree to phrasal categories. At the same time, morphological categories, syntactic structure and syntactic functions

⁴There are also unheaded structures: coordination, adordination, unspecified (for some multi-word units and other non-standard strings).

⁵This is a solution commonly used in HPSG grammars, cf. e.g. [14].

proposed by the parser are checked.

Information added from external lexica concerns mainly valency. Valency frames actually used in the treebank are derived from more general specifications in the external lexica by a set of lexical rules. The grammar and the lexical rules are specified and implemented in *Trale*, a formalism for implementing HPSG grammars.⁶

5.1 Valency lexicon

At the moment, two external valency dictionaries are used: VALLEX [9] and PDT-VALLEX [2], including about 5,000 and 10,000 verbs, respectively, with their deep valency frames and surface morphological realizations.⁷ The frames reflect the Praguean valency theory of the Functional Generative Description.⁸ The frames are used to check whether valency requirements of the verbs used in the parsed sentence are met.

The frames consist of lists of arguments together with their surface realization in an active sentence. The frames are converted to attribute-value matrices (AVM's), used by lexical rules, specifying valency properties for derived forms. The rules are implemented as a *Trale* grammar (see §5 above). The grammar produces surface frames for various forms of a given verb, namely finite indicative/imperative, passive participle, past participle, infinitive and transgressive. Different diatheses exist for these verb forms, including reflexivization. The rules are based on the following assumptions about Czech verbs (cf. [18] and [20]): (i) non-reflexive verbs in the active voice have identical deep and surface frame; (ii) reflexive verbs and verbs in deagentive constructions add a reflexive particle slot to their surface valency frame; (iii) inherent reflexives have only the active voice; (iv) non-reflexive verbs with at least two arguments, where Actor is realized by a structural case,⁹ can form periphrastic (analytical) passive; (v) non-reflexive verbs with at least one argument can form a deagentive construction; (vi) in the active voice, Actor realized by a structural case is the subject while other arguments are objects; (vii) in the passive voice and deagentive constructions, an argument different from Actor and realized by a structural case is the subject, while Actor realized by a structural case is omitted on the surface.

⁶ See <http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/hpsg/archive/projects/trale/>

⁷Verbalex [4], a valency dictionary larger than VALLEX, is another candidate. It is based on a different theory and the arguments are assigned semantic roles. We plan to use this resource as well as to offer a different classification of the arguments.

⁸The FGD theory assumes deep and surface levels of syntax. On the deep 'tectogrammatical' level, every verb frame contains up to five arguments (actants), which correspond to subject and objects on the surface level, and obligatory free modifications, which correspond to adjuncts. The arguments are called Actor, Patient, Addressee, Origin and Effect.

⁹Structural case is a case which is not assigned in the lexicon, but depends on the diathesis and/or negation of the verb. Typically, direct object in an active sentence has Accusative case, but in passive sentence, it becomes Subject in Nominative case. In Czech, there also exist Genitive of Negation and Partitive Genitive.

The surface frames are used to check the saturation of valency. As the source lexica do not contain information on possible passivization, the lexical rules over-generate for some diatheses. However, hypothetical passive forms of some verbs may never occur in the data.

5.2 Principles of grammar

As usual in HPSG grammars, the main parts, determining the syntactic skeleton of annotation, are performed by the Head Feature Principle (HFP) and the Valency Principle (ValP).¹⁰ HFP propagates head information from lexical heads up to non-terminal nodes in the tree. ValP makes sure that saturation of valency frames is checked. If this check/match is successful, arguments receive additional information, such as deep syntactic function.

Other principles are in charge of properly distributing morphosyntactic information within lexical items. This includes mainly the sharing of values determined by the form itself and its valency requirements. The lexical rules in §5.1, handling the relation between deep and surface valency, can be seen as expressing the Linking Principle. The Surface Function Assignment Principle, the Case Principle and the Agreement Principle take care of other respective phenomena.

Due to the absence of other principles, e.g. those governing word order, the grammar overgenerates, but this will be gradually remedied as the grammar is developed further.

5.3 Analytical verb forms

Standard grammars of Czech treat analytical forms as a morphological rather than syntactic phenomenon. Tense, mood and voice are seen as morphological categories, interpreting grammatical meanings of content verbs, often requiring auxiliary forms. On the other hand, most approaches within corpus or theoretical linguistics assume that morphological categories do not span word boundaries.

To reconcile these two perspectives, content words have an additional analytical dimension with the three properties of tense, mood and voice. Their values are determined by the grammar, operating on specifications from the lexicon, rather than by any device targeting individual orthographical words. The grammar treats analytical forms as syntactic phrases, consisting of a function word as the surface head and a content word (or a phrase including a content word), as the deep head.¹¹ The details are encoded in the lexical specifications of function words, the rest is the task of a general valency satisfaction mechanism (ValP) and a rule projecting features of the head daughter to its phrasal mother (HFP).

¹⁰In addition to the definition of possible data types and their properties in the signature part of the grammar.

¹¹It is the surface head which is the parallel of *head* in standard HPSG grammars. The head of the whole structure is the finite (personal) form. This is true also about analytical forms including more than one auxiliary, such as past conditional: the (surface) head of *byl bys přijel* 'you would have arrived' is the 2nd position clitic *bys* 'would'.

Other multi-word units, such as idioms, are also annotated by co-indexing the relevant lexical nodes, which do not always form a phrase (subtree). The annotation is based on a collocation lexicon, derived from [22], see [8].

6 Evaluation

Four key stages of processing an input sentence were evaluated: (i) accuracy of morphological annotation; (ii) accuracy of stochastic dependency parsing against the data from the Prague Dependency Treebank (PDT);¹² (iii) accuracy of the conversion of dependency parses to constituency-based structures, and (iv) accuracy of the conversion of the string-like morphological and POS tags to typed feature structures;

(i) **Morphological annotation.** The accuracy of morphological annotation including morphological analysis and disambiguation (the rule-based cooperating with a stochastic one) is 94.57% (cf. [19]).

(ii) **Stochastic dependency parsing.** MaltParser was tested automatically on the d-test data set of the PDT. Using the method of text simplification (see §3 above), it achieves an unlabeled accuracy of 86.76% and a labeled accuracy of 81.21% on single tokens. If counted for entire sentences, the accuracy is 44.52% (unlabeled) and 34.01% (labeled, i.e. a third of sentences is parsed correctly).

(iii) **Conversion from dependency to phrase structures.** The conversion of 400 sentences whose dependency structure was manually annotated in accordance with the PDT Annotation Manual¹³ was manually checked. 21 input sentences (5.25%) were assigned incorrect dependency annotation, but we evaluated only the conversion proper, regardless of whether the input dependency structure was correctly annotated or not. There were 15 sentences (3.75%) incorrectly converted due to the following reasons: (a) subject is expressed by a prepositional phrase, (b) subject is a coordination, itself modified by a coordination of attributes, (c) a coordination of verbal predicates is combined with overt subject, (d) a reflexive particle does not form a constituent with its base verb, (e) errors in transformation rules: (e1) a verbal attribute modifies a noun rather than a verb, (e2) cardinal numerals are converted as heads rather than as surface heads. Moreover, 57 input sentences included the function label ExD (*External Dependent*) attached to a node lacking its mother node (ellipsis). Such structures were correctly converted by a default rule, while ExD structures should be treated separately (see below).

The errors of type (a)–(f) can be rectified in a relatively simple way. As for ExD, there are two solutions: in most elliptical structures the mother node of a converted ExD element will have the *gap* feature flagged; the remaining cases, such as comparative structures (*němý jako ryba* ‘mute as a fish’), will be annotated as non-elliptical.

(iv) **Conversion of the string-like morphological and POS tags to typed feature**

¹²See <http://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/pdt3.0>

¹³See <https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/pdt2.0/doc/manuals/cz/a-layer/html>

structures. The total of 200 input word forms were manually checked. On input, every word form was assigned a lemma and a string-like morphological tag. This annotation was transformed to a typed feature structure (Fig. 3 in §4). The only conversion problems were caused by lexical lemmas (lLemma, see also §4 above) of deverbal nouns and deverbal adjectives: 5 word forms were assigned incorrect lexical lemmas. This can be remedied by corrections of conversion tables.

7 Discussion and perspectives

The annotation of language structures in the treebank of Czech and the main features of the formal grammar licensing these structures is the core of the project. Despite the limited coverage of grammatical phenomena the feasibility of the concept has already been verified on less complex syntactic structures.

The grammar is still very permissive but this will be gradually remedied by more grammatical constraints (e.g. for capturing word order phenomena). We shall also be concerned with the issue of preserving/restoring structural ambiguity in the data. However, the perspective of further development of the treebank data annotation and the grammar concern all stages of processing input data. Especially the quality of parsing should be further improved: by tuning the parser to cope with specific features of Czech and by using multiple parsers in a voting scenario. The valency lexicon will be further developed in several directions: we will continue to test valency frames in the VALLEX lexicon (and other lexica such as [4]) on real data and add frames for more verbs will be added. Moreover, the pilot search and data visualisation and export/import options will be developed to interact with the corpus data and to handle various visualization formats such constituency vs. dependency, surface and deep structure).

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